

Application of 1-(1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)-3-phenylurea as a sensing material in construction of Tm^{3+} -ion selective electrochemical sensor

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Abstract : A Tm^{3+} -PVC membrane ion-selective electrode has been fabricated based on 1-(1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)-3-phenylurea (IPU) as a suitable sensing material. The sensor exhibits a linear dynamic range of 1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2} M with a Nernstian slope of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade of thulium concentration and a detection limit of 6.3×10^{-7} M. A quick response time for the sensor (smaller than 10 s) was observed, and the electrode was found to work in the pH range of 2.4–9.8. The recommended sensor revealed comparatively good selectivity with respect to most alkali, alkaline earth, some transition and heavy metal ions. To assess its analytical applicability the proposed Tm^{3+} sensor was successfully employed as an indicator electrode in the titration of Tm^{3+} ion with EDTA and the Tm^{3+} determination in binary mixtures.

Keywords : PVC membrane, sensor, potentiometry, ion-selective electrode.

Introduction

Thulium is one of the rare earth elements. Thulium is used as a dopant in tunable fiber lasers and the thulium oxide compounds are used in portable sources of diagnostic X-ray devices¹. The commonly methods for the low-level detection of Tm^{3+} ions in solutions are isotope dilution mass spectrometry, neutron activation analysis, X-ray fluorescence spectrometry, ICP-MS, ICP-AES and spectrofluorimetry. These techniques are all very accurate and precise; however, they are expensive and need complicated equipments. Potentiometry by ISEs is a fast, inexpensive and simple method for determination of ions. By this method, we have recently introduced a number of lanthanide selective membrane sensors for the determination of lanthanides²⁻¹⁷, but there is just some reports on measurement of thulium by ion selective electrode¹⁸⁻²⁰. In this paper, we wish to introduce a new Tm^{3+} PVC-based membrane sensor based on 1-(1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)-3-phenylurea (IPU) (Fig. 1) as a suitable ionophore.

Experimental

Reagents :

The chemicals of analytical reagent grade were purchased from Aldrich Co. Chloride and nitrate salts of the

Fig. 1. The IPU chemical structure.

used cations), Fluka (high-molecular weight polyvinylchloride and benzyl acetate (BA)) and Merck (dibutylphthalate (DBP)), nitrobenzene (NB), the chloride and nitrate salts of the used cations and acetophenone (AP). The ligand 1-(1,3-dioxoisindolin-2-yl)-3-phenylurea was synthesized and purified as described elsewhere²¹. All solutions were prepared using doubly distilled deionized water.

The membrane preparation :

Membrane solutions were prepared by thoroughly dissolving 3 mg of IPU, 30 mg of powdered PVC, 65 mg of DBP and 2.0 mg of NaTPB in 5 mL of fresh THF. After mixing the solution, it was transferred into a glass dish of 2 cm in diameter. Next, the THF content of the mixture was let to evaporate slowly, to obtain an oily concentrated mixture. A Pyrex tube (3–5 mm o.d. on top) was dipped into the mixture for about 10 s, so that a transpar-

ent membrane of about 0.3 mm thickness was formed²²⁻³⁵. The tube was pulled out from the mixture and kept at room temperature for a period of half a day. The tube was then filled with an internal solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TmCl_3$). The electrode was finally conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TmCl_3$ solution. A silver/silver chloride electrode was used as an internal reference electrode.

The EMF measurements :

The EMF measurements were carried out with the following cell assembly :

Ag-AgCl | internal solution, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $TmCl_3$ | PVC membrane | test solution | Hg-Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (satd.)

Using a Corning ion analyzer 250 pH/mV meter at 25.0 °C.

The activities of the ions tested were calculated according to the Debye-Huckel procedure³⁶.

Results and discussion

In order to study IPU as a suitable ion carrier towards Tm^{3+} ion, it was used to prepare PVC membrane electrodes for a wide variety of alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. Only the Tm^{3+} ion illustrated a strong response (with a slope of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade) to the IPU-based membrane electrodes in comparison with the other different metal ions tested. Among the different cations, Tm^{3+} with the most sensitive response seems to be suitably determined with the PVC-based membrane based on IPU. This observation can be attributed to the selective behavior of the PVC membrane system against Tm^{3+} in comparison with the tested metal

ions, including other lanthanide ions.

The influence of membrane composition :

Since the sensitivity and selectivity obtained for a given ionophore depend significantly on the membrane ingredients, the nature of solvent mediator and additive used³⁷⁻⁴⁰. The presence of lipophilic anions in a cation-selective membranes based on neutral carrier not only diminishes the ohmic resistance and enhances the response behavior and selectivity but also, in cases where the extraction capability is poor, increases the sensitivity of the membrane electrodes⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. We investigated the influences of membrane compositions on the potential responses of the Tm^{3+} sensor. The results are summarized in Table 1 and the results showed that the membrane, which contained 3 mg of IPU, 65 mg of DBP, 2 mg of NaTPB and 30 mg of PVC had a rather sensitive response of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV/decade of Tm^{3+} concentration. To find the best plasticizer for the membrane for common plasticizers namely NB, AP, BA and DBP were used in an amount of 66 mg (Nos. 1-4, Table 1). BA, NB and AP showed the responses of 17.8 ± 0.2 , 17.1 ± 0.6 and 16.9 ± 0.5 mV per decade respectively. However, the best responses were observed in the case of DBP with a response of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade.

The Tm^{3+} sensor evaluation :

To evaluate the proposed sensor, after conditioning the membranes with the same composition for different time periods in a 0.01 M thulium chloride solution, the potential response of the Tm^{3+} PVC-based membrane sensor at varying concentrations of thulium solution (concentration range from 1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) was

Table 1. Optimization of the membrane ingredients

Sensor No.	Composition (wt. %)				Slope (mV/decade)	Concentration range (M)
	PVC	Plasticizer	NaTPB	IPU		
1	30	NB, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	17.1 ± 0.6
2	30	BA, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	17.8 ± 0.2
3	30	AP, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	16.9 ± 0.5
4	30	DBP, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	18.5 ± 0.4
5	30	DBP, 68	0	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	14.8 ± 0.4
6	30	DBP, 67	1	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	17.7 ± 0.6
7	30	DBP, 65	3	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	18.2 ± 0.3
8	30	DBP, 67	2	1	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	16.7 ± 0.5
9	30	DBP, 65	2	3	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	20.8 ± 0.4

investigated (Fig. 2). The slope of calibration graph was the optimum value of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade of the activity of Tm^{3+} ions and the detection limit of the sensor, determined from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph was 6.3×10^{-7} M.

Fig. 2. Calibration curves of the IPU-based Tm^{3+} sensor.

The pH effect :

The impact of test-solution pH on the sensor response was tested over a pH range of 1.5–11.0 by measuring the potential response of the sensor at a 1.0×10^{-3} M of Tm^{3+} ion concentration (Fig. 3) using concentrated NaOH or HCl. As can be seen, the potential in the pH range of 2.4–9.8 has remained relatively constant. The observed potential drift at the higher pH values may be due to the formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Tm^{3+} in the solution. At the lower pH values, the potentials have increased, indicating that the membrane sensor responds to hydrogen ions.

Fig. 3. pH effect of the test solution (1.0×10^{-3} M of Tm^{3+}) of the Tm^{3+} sensor based on IPU.

Dynamic response time of the Tm3+ sensor :

The dynamic response time of the Tm^{3+} sensor based IPU was measured at various concentrations (1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M) and the results are shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen, the electrode reaches its equilibrium response in a very short time (< 10 s) in the whole concentration range.

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the proposed sensor based on IPU for step changes in the Tm^{3+} concentration : (A) 1.0×10^{-6} M, (B) 1.0×10^{-5} M, (C) 1.0×10^{-4} M, (D) 1.0×10^{-3} M, (E) 1.0×10^{-2} M.

Selectivity coefficient determination of the Tm3+ sensor :

The selectivity behavior is obviously one of the most important characteristics of an ion-selective electrode, determining the feasibility of a reliable measurement in the target sample. To investigate the membrane electrode selectivity, its potential response was monitored in the presence of various interfering foreign cations using the matched potential method (MPM)⁴⁵⁻⁵¹ and the selectivity coefficients of the membrane sensor are given in Table 2. In line with the information of this Table, the selectivity coefficients for the monovalent and the divalent tested cations (Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+}) are smaller than 8.0×10^{-4} . Additionally, the selectivity coefficients for the divalent trivalent cations (Dy^{3+} , Yb^{3+} , Ho^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Eu^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Lu^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+}) are relatively small (from 7.6×10^{-4} to 5.3×10^{-3}). The resultant selectivity coefficients indicate that they can not disturb the function of the Tm^{3+} membrane electrode.

Table 3 shows the comparison of previously reported thulium ion selective sensor with the proposed sensor¹⁸⁻²⁰. As it can be seen, the proposed sensor in terms of selec-

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients ($K_{Tm^{3+},B}^{MPM}$) of proposed Tm^{3+} sensor

Interfering ions	$K_{Tm^{3+},B}^{MPM}$	Interfering ions	$K_{Tm^{3+},B}^{MPM}$
Dy ³⁺	4.9×10^{-3}	Fe ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}
Yb ³⁺	5.3×10^{-3}	Cr ³⁺	4.7×10^{-3}
Ho ³⁺	8.7×10^{-4}	Na ⁺	4.7×10^{-4}
Gd ³⁺	2.2×10^{-3}	Ca ²⁺	6.4×10^{-4}
Nd ³⁺	8.4×10^{-4}	Zn ²⁺	8.0×10^{-4}
Sm ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}	Co ²⁺	7.5×10^{-4}
Eu ³⁺	3.2×10^{-3}	Cd ²⁺	6.3×10^{-4}
Er ³⁺	7.6×10^{-4}	Ni ²⁺	6.7×10^{-4}
Pr ³⁺	2.6×10^{-3}	Pb ²⁺	7.8×10^{-4}
Lu ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}	-	-

tivity coefficient and detection limit is superior to the previous reported ones.

Analytical application :

The suggested Tm^{3+} PVC-membrane sensor was found to work well under the laboratory conditions. The selective Tm^{3+} membrane sensor was used as an indicator

electrode in the titration of a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M Tm^{3+}$ ion solution with a standard $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ EDTA. The resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 5. As it can be seen from this Figure, the sensor is capable of monitoring the amount of thulium ions.

The proposed Tm^{3+} sensor was also used to the direct determination of Tm^{3+} ions in binary mixtures. The corresponding results in Table 4 reveal that the Tm^{3+}

Fig. 5. Potential titration curves of 20.0 mL $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M Tm^{3+}$ solution with $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ of EDTA.

Table 3. Comparison of previously reported Tm^{3+} sensor with the proposed sensor

Ion	Ref. 18	Ref. 19	Ref. 20	This work
Linearity range (mol L ⁻¹)	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$
Detection limit (mol L ⁻¹)	4.0×10^{-7}	8.0×10^{-6}	8.7×10^{-7}	6.3×10^{-7}
Response time (s)	15	7	~10	<10
Slope (mV/decade)	19.5	19.5	19.5	20.8
$K_{MPM} > 10^{-2}$	Er, Lu, Yb, Pb	Er, Nd, Ho, Mg	Lu, Yb	-

Table 4. Determination of Tm^{3+} ions in binary mixtures

Tm^{3+} (M)	Added cation (M)	Found ^a (M)	Recovery (%)
5.0×10^{-4}	Dy ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.85 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-4}$	97.0
5.0×10^{-4}	Yb ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.89 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-4}$	97.8
5.0×10^{-4}	Ho ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.94 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4}$	97.8
5.0×10^{-4}	Nd ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.97 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-4}$	99.4
5.0×10^{-4}	Er ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.93 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-4}$	98.6
5.0×10^{-4}	Sm ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(5.12 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4}$	102.4
5.0×10^{-4}	Gd ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(5.17 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-4}$	103.4
5.0×10^{-4}	Cr ³⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.87 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4}$	97.4
5.0×10^{-4}	Na ⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.96 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-4}$	99.2
5.0×10^{-4}	Ca ²⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(5.08 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-4}$	101.6
5.0×10^{-4}	Ni ²⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(5.04 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-4}$	100.8
5.0×10^{-4}	Pb ²⁺ , 5.0×10^{-2}	$(4.98 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-4}$	99.6

^aResults are based on three measurements.

ions recovery is quantitative and they support the fact that the thulium membrane sensor can be used for the direct Tm^{3+} monitoring in real samples.

Conclusion :

The results of this research showed that the potentiometric PVC membrane sensor based on IPU functions as a suitable Tm^{3+} selective electrode can be used for the determination of Tm^{3+} ion in the presence of common interfering ions. The sensor has been shown to have good operating characteristic : (i) a slope of 20.8 ± 0.4 mV per decade, (ii) low limit of detection (6.3×10^{-7} M), (iii) pH range (2.4–9.8), (iv) fast response time (< 10 s) and wide linear range (1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2} M). The proposed sensor was applied for the determination of thulium ion in different solution samples.

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